

MAGNETISM AND CATALYSIS. PART IV. CATALYSIS OF THE REACTION BETWEEN AMMONIUM OXALATE AND MERCURIC CHLORIDE BY FERRIC IONS.

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The influence of ferric ions in catalysing the reaction between ammonium oxalate and mercuric chloride has been studied from magnetic standpoint. Results indicate that a new intermediate compound having a lower paramagnetic susceptibility value than that of ferric chloride is formed. It has not, however, been possible to ascertain definitely whether this intermediate compound is ferrous chloride or ferrous oxalate.

Much speculation is rife as regards the mechanism of the catalytic reaction between mercuric chloride and ammonium oxalate. Planche (*J. Pharm.*, 1815, 49), Becquerel and Beny ("La Lumière ses causes et ses effets" 1868), and later on Eder investigated the reaction thoroughly and showed that the reaction is a photochemical one and can be represented as

Kastle and Beatty (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1900, 24, 182) showed that this reaction is accelerated by the presence of ferric and uranyl salts whereas it is retarded by the presence of chromates and chromic acid.

Winther (*Z. wiss. Phot.*, 1909, 7, 409; 1910, 8, 237, 197) suggested that the reaction in the Eder's solution proceeds through the intermediate formation of ferrous chloride which further reduces mercuric chloride to mercurous chloride. The reaction can be represented as

Winther (*ibid.*, 1919, 17, 409) later on studied in detail the influence of various catalysts on the reaction and observed that ferric salts, when present in small concentrations, accelerate the reaction whereas when they are present in larger concentrations, they act as inhibitors. Winther suggested that in the presence of catalysts, the reaction proceeds through the formation of ferrous oxalate which in its turn reduces mercuric chloride to mercurous chloride. The whole mechanism could be represented as

Berger (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1921, 40, 387) carried out systematic study of this reaction and concluded the view that the reaction takes place between the mercuric and oxalate ions as untenable. He, however, completely neglected the influence of iron salts in explaining his view.

The present investigation has thus been undertaken to clarify the reaction mechanism from magnetic standpoint.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The purity of the materials used was of a very high order. B. D. H. analytical reagents were purified and used. In the case of solutions, susceptibility has been calculated with the help of the relation

$$\chi_{\text{soln}} = \chi_{\text{salt}} \times C_{\text{salt}} + \chi_{\text{solvent}} (1 - C_{\text{salt}}).$$

Specific susceptibilities of the solution of the same order of strength as were to be used in the reaction were also determined and this relationship found to be valid.

The following solutions were prepared in conductivity water of which the susceptibility value had been determined: (i) 0.10N-mercuric chloride; (ii) 0.101N-ammonium oxalate. In mixing up the solution, 100 c.c. of 0.10N-mercuric chloride were taken in a flask and 99 c.c. of 0.101N-ammonium oxalate were added followed by 1 c.c. of FeCl_3 of known strength.

The whole mixture was then immediately exposed to sunlight for definite periods of time. Three different samples were exposed each time and six readings were taken at different intervals. After the required exposure the flasks were carried immediately to a dark room and connected to a vacuum pump to remove any dissolved carbon dioxide evolved during the reaction. The filtrate was made up to 250 c.c. in conductivity water. All these operations were carried out in a dark room under red light. The susceptibility of these solutions was determined on a modified form of Guoy's balance. Exposure of sunlight was avoided on account of the reaction being photochemical. It was observed, however, that if great care was not taken in keeping the exposed samples, either when estimating their constituents or when determining their susceptibility, in complete absence of sunlight, the readings obtained were not reproducible. The chemical analysis of these solutions was also, carried out side by side, by estimating the unreacted oxalate by the usual potassium permanganate method and the unreacted HgCl_2 by estimating it as HgS .

The results of these determinations are tabulated in Table II. The theoretical values of χ were calculated on the following data (Table I).

TABLE I.

Compound.	$\chi \times 10^6$.	Reference.
Ammonium oxalate	-0.527	(Author's)
Mercuric chloride	-0.298	"
Ferrous oxalate	+67.48	"
Ferrous chloride	+101.2	(International Critical Tables)
Ferric chloride	+82.05	(Author's)
Ammonium chloride	-0.640	(International Critical Tables)

TABLE II.

HgCl₂ = 100 c.c. Am. oxalate = 99 c.c. FeCl₃ = 1 c.c. Total vol. = 200 c.c.

Time (min.).	Soln. containing unreacted oxalate (c.c.).	Chemical analysis.		χ of solution calc. on mixture law.	χ of solution observed.		χ of conductivity water.	FeCl ₃ (%).	Volume of final solution (c.c.).
		(C.c. of N/10 ²⁰ KMnO ₄ used.	Normality of unreacted oxalate.		I	II			
0 50	51.5	0.101	-0.709 × 10 ⁻⁶	-0.709 × 10 ⁻⁶	-0.708 × 10 ⁻⁶	-0.729 × 10 ⁻⁶	1.002	250	
3 50	17.25	0.033	-0.715	-0.715	-0.716	-0.721	1.002	250	
6 50	11.85	0.023	-0.721	-0.722	-0.723	-0.728	1.002	250	
12 50	10.25	0.020	-0.718	-0.721	-0.721	-0.729	1.001	250	
60 50	4.70	0.009	-0.716	-0.716	-0.718	-0.729	1.076	250	
360 50	2.15	0.004	-0.710	-0.710	-0.710	-0.727	1.043	250	

DISCUSSION.

In the case of this reaction the magnetic data (Table II) reveal that:—

- At initial stages the mixture law is obeyed.
- At intermediate stages, there is a distinct tendency of increase in the susceptibility values of the solution towards diamagnetism. This is to an extent of 0.43%.
- At the final stages, the mixture law again holds good.

These results indicate that a new intermediate compound having a lower paramagnetic susceptibility value than that of the ferric chloride is formed in the intermediate stages.

According to the two views put forward by Winther, the reaction takes place either through the formation of ferrous oxalate or ferrous chloride as an intermediary compound.

The molecular susceptibilities of ferric chloride, ferrous chloride and ferrous oxalate are $13333 \cdot 125 \times 10^{-6}$, 12852×10^{-6} and 9717×10^{-6} respectively.

If the reaction proceeds through the formation of ferrous oxalate as an intermediary compound, and whole of the ferric chloride is converted to ferrous oxalate, which is generally not the case, the susceptibility of the solution ought to show a marked increase in the diamagnetism of the solution. On the other hand, if the reaction proceeds through the formation of ferrous chloride the susceptibility of the solution would not differ much from that when ferric chloride is present there and this may be responsible for the small difference between the experimental and calculated susceptibility values of the reacting solutions. It may be argued that in the reaction under investigation, whole of the ferric chloride is not converted to ferrous oxalate as is generally the case in catalytic reactions and thereby the effect produced on the magnetic properties of the solution due to the formation of ferrous oxalate as an intermediary compound is not appreciable, and thus the difference between the observed and calculated susceptibility values of the solution is not marked. Formation of ferrous oxalate as an intermediary compound in the reaction is further supported by Winther who observed that ferrous oxalate reduces mercuric chloride even in the dark at room temperature.

From the magnetic data, although it is not possible to say definitely whether ferrous chloride or ferrous oxalate is formed as an intermediate compound yet it shows that the reaction is definitely proceeding through the formation of intermediate compound.

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